

COLONIAL INTERESTS AND PROMOTION TO GOLD MINING IN KOLAR REGION DURING THE DEWANSHIP OF K. SHESHADRI IYER IN PRINCELY MYSORE

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ABSTRACT

The period of Dewan Sheshadri Iyer was a significant period in the administrative annals of Princely state of Mysore. The regime saw an explorative expansion of Mysore state & this led to the branching out of Princely state of Mysore towards affirmative progression. This paper focuses on the significant political moves behind promotion of Railways, Hydro electric Projects, & such other projects during the Dewan Sheshadri Iyer. The Indirect colonial rule was holding the reigns of administration & controlling it through the Dewans. Even though the portrayal of Dewans as proactive & progressive Administrators, there was a drive to make colonial benefit fulfilled. This paper focuses on the developmental activities under the Dewanship of Sheshadri Iyer who monitored great public welfare projects only to benefit the Gold mining in Kolar region.

Keywords: Dewan Sheshadri Iyer, Gold mining, colonial interests in Kolar gold mining, benefits for gold mining companies

INTRODUCTION:

Princely state of Mysore needed to augment the sources of revenue as it had to pay the obligatory subsidies to Colonial British Government. After Rendition of the State in 1881 the economic resources were revamped because the subsidy amount was too heavy for Mysorean exchequer. There were Dewans who guided the De Jure Wodeyar King about management of finances & economic resources. Dewan K Sheshadri Iyer who took office as Dewan in 1883 was one such visionary administrator who envisioned the potential growth of Mysore through various developmental projects. Gold mining was one such area which he perceived as the prospective growth area. Kolar became highly populated areas with nearly 1 lakh population. Nearly 25, 000 work force from neighboring Andhra region & Tamil nadu regions flocked to Kolar to work in Gold fields. Nearly 500 British Officials were involved in the management of the Gold fields. All the top position were held by them. Anglo Indians also were influential While the labor were brought with their contractors. Devoid of any basic necessities there were toiling day in & day out in severe working conditions. But Kolar was fetching them good source of income . The colonial interests were met out of this income in a great way. Kolar became a highly populated areas with nearly 1 lakh population. Nearly 25 ,000 work force from neighboring Andhra region & Tamil nadu regions flocked to Kolar to work in Gold fields. Nearly 500 British Officials were involved in the management of the Gold fields. All the top position were held by them. Anglo Indians also were influential While the labor were brought with their contractors . Devoid of any basic necessities there were toiling day in & day out in severe working conditions. But

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Dewan Sheshadri Iyer

Sheshadri Iyer was appointed Judicial Secretary in the Ashtagram division in 1868. He later served as Head Sheristadar of the Court of the Judicial Commissioner, Assistant Commissioner of Mysore, Deputy Commissioner and District Magistrate of Tumkur and District and Sessions Judge of Ashtagram division. He was appointed as Dewan of Mysore After C Rangacharlu.

References to gold mining in Kolar region

Kolar gold mining & its history has been compiled by Father Reverend Fred Goodwill which has been published in the Mythic society journals . Gold mining has a long history in this region. Historical searches have been very accurate to traces of mining in this region.

1. **References Of Mining In Harappan sites** - Historical reference to gold mining in the Kolar region has been compiled & reconstructed references to gold in Harappa sites with 11% purity index
2. **References by Pliny**-Greek Historian Pliny who toured India during first century AD refers to gold mining in India
3. **References Of Mining In Gupta Period** – there are references to gold mining in southern parts of India during Gupta period .
4. **References Of Mining In Chola period** - there are references to gold mining in southern parts of India during Chola period
5. **References Of Mining In Vijayanagara kings**- there are references to gold mining in southern parts of India during Vijayanagara period
6. **References Of Mining during Tipusultan** - there are references to gold mining in southern parts of India during Tipu's reign as he was mobilizing all his economic resources against the British. He had a very interesting industrial expansion during his tenure.

The stages of modern mining in Kolar region

In 1873 M F Lavelle who was an Irish Soldier settled in Bangalore was an experienced man in mining as he had participated in wars in New Zealand, approached the Government of Mysore with a request to mine in Kolar region. His work of mining began in 1875. But the work of mining was a great investment project incurring huge sums of capital investment. Finding the capital too exhaustive Mr. Lavelle transferred the mining rights to Major General G Pore Beresford in 1876 .

Major General G Pore Beresford & his attempts in Kolar

Major General G Pore Beresford evolving a new strategy to mining projects, formed a syndicate popularly known as Kolar Concessionaries soft corporation & Arbuthnot of Madras. Major General G Pore Beresford was a delighted person to start his work according to a well laid out plan & acquired the adjoining areas & this included the present Kolar Gold fields. However, large-scale mining only came in the 1890s under the British firm John Taylor & Company which did much of the prospecting and mining with more skilled manpower and sophisticated machinery. A railways line connecting Bangarupete & Marikuppam was taken up it connected all the mines. It connected Kolar with Bangalore Madras railway Line the Colonial government indirectly financed the construction of this railways line . In 1902 the power generation was started at Shivanasamudram in order to light up

Kolar gold mining regions. The British resident Sir Robertson was instrument in making this Hydro electric project . Bethamangala drinking water project was taken up the Mysore government because the mining population both laborers & officials suffered from shortage of drinking water . The population in Kolar Gold mining region was increasing by leaps & bounds as there were nearly 23 thousand laborers & 500 European civilians .

CONCLUSION

There was a great impulsive administrative moves during the period of Dewan K Sheshadri Iyer , The development to Gold fields was an implication of such move. The implication behind the development of KGF was driven not by the necessities of the local population but to fill the capital demands of British officials. Kolar became a highly populated areas with nearly 1 lakh population . Nearly 25 ,000 work force from neighboring Andhra region & Tamil nadu regions flocked to Kolar to work in Gold fields. Nearly 500 British Officials were involved in the management of the Gold fields. All the top position were held by them. Anglo Indians also were influential While the labor were brought with their contractors . Devoid of any basic necessities there were toiling day in & day out in severe working conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Itihaasa Darshana Volumes 2010-2011-2012
2. Suryanatha Kamat- A Concise history of Karnataka 2012 Jupiter publication Bangalore
3. C. Hayavadana Rao (1946), History of Mysore (1399–1799 A.D.): Incorporating the Latest Epigraphically, Literary and Historical Researches, Volume III (1766–1799), Bangalore: Government Press.
4. Mysore gazetteer 1935 Government of Mysore publication
5. Ramusack, Barbara (2004), The Indian Princes and their States (The New Cambridge History of India), Cambridge and London: Cambridge University Press
6. Bhagavan, Manu (2008), "Princely States and the Hindu Imaginary: Exploring the Cartography of Hindu Nationalism in Colonial India", The Journal of Asian Studies 67 (3)
7. Simmons, Colin (1985), "'De-Industrialization', Industrialization and the Indian Economy, c. 1850–1947", Modern Asian Studies 19 (3)
8. Aya Ikegame-Princely India Re-imagined- “ A Historical Anthropology of Mysore from 1799 to the present” Published 22nd August 2012 by Routledge